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WEARABLE TECH AND THE CASUALIZATION OF BIOMETRIC SURVEILLANCE IN WELLNESS CULTURE

ABSTRACT

This paper explores manifestations of ableism in online wellness and wearables tech cultures, and in turn, criticizes the idea that technology is a quick remedy to physical debility. It highlights two distinct but related Internet cultures: those of nondisabled people who attempt to achieve wellness by using wearable, biometric devices and, alternatively, those consisting of the disabled and chronically ill people who must use biotechnologies to survive. I assert that much of the wearable tech nondisabled people become infatuated with obscures socioeconomic discrepancies in labor time, personal time, and wealth that contribute to reduced states of wellness

in the first place. In contrast to discourses around biohacking, I focus on realistic depictions of the multivariant forms of pride and frustration that constitute what disability scholars refer to as ‘cyborg life.’ I contend that these representations offer insight into disabled culture that is missing in popular, nondisabled representations of technology, and as such challenge the notion that more and better technology is the answer to healthy, equitable futures.

KEYWORDS: disability, technoableism, surveillance, capitalism, biotechnologies, wearable tech

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INTRODUCTION: FROM DISABILITY PRIDE TO DISABILITY PRECARITY

The term “disability precarity” was proposed by disability writer and activist Alice Wong in July 2023, when she posted on Twitter: “Instead of #DisabilityPrideMonth, how about #DisabilityPrecarityMonth where we organize and fight like hell?” Wong explained her position by saying that “pride is complicated and flattens out a lot of the joy, love, and care that is intertwined with pain, systemic ableism, and trauma.”² Disability precarity invokes in its broadest sense the inequality that the disabled people face every day in a world organized for non-disabled people. Reading disability as a position of precarity—rather than always emphasizing pride—allows for a greater understanding of the myriad systems that enable, and conversely, limit, disabled embodiments, networks, and attachments.

Ironically, the transformation of Twitter—where #disabilityprecarity first circulated—from a popular space for #HashtagActivism into a space less welcoming of inclusive and fact-based expression represents one form of precarity experienced by disabled people (Jarreat-Poole par. 8).³ That is, once Twitter (now “X”) was acquired by Elon Musk in October 2022, the platform began to deregulate hate speech and loosen checks on credibility. In June 2023, for instance, the Center for Countering Digital Hate reported that “Twitter fails to act on 99% of hate posted by verified users.” More specifically, the platform “failed to acts on tweets containing racist, homophobic, neo-Nazi or antisemitic conspiracy” over the several weeks leading up to their reporting.⁴ Similarly, University of California Berkley News reported in February 2025 that “weekly rates of hate speech on the social media platform X rose about 50% in the months after its purchase in October 2022 by Elon Musk.”⁵ As disability Twitter long connected its members to mutual aid resources and survival wisdom, its dissolution showcases the instability of access networks.⁶

² Alice Wong 王美華 (@SFdirewolf), “...Pride is complicated and flattens out a lot of the joy, love, and care that is intertwined with pain, systemic ableism, and trauma,” Twitter (now X), July 2, 2023, <https://x.com/SFdirewolf/status/1675588957793550337>.

³ For a discussion around hashtagging as a complicated form of disability coalescence, see Adan Jarreat-Poole, “Crip Encounters in the Corporate Hashtag: Complicating #BellLetsTalk,” *Disability Studies Quarterly* 43, no. 3 (2024), <https://dsq-sds.org/index.php/dsq/article/view/7860/8131>. See also: Sarah Jackson, Moya Bailey, and Brooke Foucault Welles, *#HashtagActivism: Networks of Race and Gender Justice* (Cambridge: MIT Press, 2020).

⁴ “Twitter Fails to Act on 99% of Twitter Blue Accounts Tweeting Hate,” Center for Countering Digital Hate, June 1, 2023, para. 4, <https://counterhate.com/research/twitter-fails-to-act-on-twitter-blue-accounts-tweeting-hate/>.

⁵ Kara Manke, “Study Finds Persistent Spike in Hate Speech on X,” Berkeley News, February 13, 2025, para. 1, <https://news.berkeley.edu/2025/02/13/study-finds-persistent-spike-in-hate-speech-on-x/>.

⁶ In “The Vibes Are Off: Did Elon Musk Push Academics Off Twitter?” James Bisbee and Kevin Munger explain, “Musk’s ownership brought a range of changes to the platform, including mass layoffs at Twitter; the reinstatement of ex-president Donald Trump’s account which had been deactivated following its role in the January 6, 2021, riots at the Capitol; the reinstatement of thousands of accounts that had been suspended for violating the platform’s Terms of Service; the corresponding

These negative trends are not limited to Twitter, however. For instance, as of January 2025, Meta has updated its “Hateful Conduct” policy to now permit ableist, homophobic, and transphobic language and classification systems. In their open letter to Meta CEO Mark Zuckerberg, the Center for Democracy and Technology explains, Meta’s Hateful Conduct Policy “will now allow far more anti-LGBTQ, racist, anti-immigrant, and ableist content on Meta’s services globally,” permitting, for example, “allegations of mental illness or abnormality when based on gender or sexual orientation” in religious and political discourse.⁷ And in the United States, cuts to federal funding for health programs and research—such as the National Institutes of Health (NIH) and Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC)—will render information and resources to prevent and treat illness even more scarce.

At the same time as health resources are being rationed, censored, and defunded, digital health technologies are ever expanding within our media ecosystem. This article suggests, drawing on Alice Wong’s concept of “disability precarity,” that current media ecosystems exacerbate ableism by promoting misconceptions on the relationship between health, technology, and individual agency. Guided by key terms and concepts in disability studies, media studies, and science and technology studies (STS), I examine the relationship between disability precarity and what disability scholar Adan Jerreat-Poole appropriately labels as “prescriptive wellness,” which frames health as a matter of individual lifestyle choice.⁸ While disability experience is often marked by concerns around access to and efficacy of survival technologies, media studies scholar Anita Ray Chan argues, health technologies are increasingly instrumentalized to affirm “the respectability, worth, and value” of nondisabled people with relative access to surplus time, money, and mobility.⁹

BIOMETRIC TECHNOLOGY, SURVEILLANCE, AND CYBORGS

In this article, I understand “biometric technology” as any technology that measures and/or responds to health information, and “wearable technology” as a form of biometric technology typically worn on the body, e.g. in the form of a watch, band, or

permission of posts containing mis/disinformation that had previously been barred; as well as a general weakening of the enforcement of these scaled-back policies (Bisbee and Munger, “The Vibes Are Off,” 139). For more on these transformations, see Louise Vallée, “Losing the Last Thread,” *Slate*, November 14, 2022, <https://slate.com/technology/2022/11/twitter-disability-chronic-illness-community-diagnosis-medical-funds.html>.

⁷ See Alexandra Reeve Givens and Kate Ruane, “Letter from Meta Civil Rights Advisory Group Members on Grave Concerns with Content Policy Changes,” *Center for Democracy and Technology*, January 14, 2025, <https://cdt.org/insights/letter-meta-civil-rights-advisory-group-members-grave-concerns-content-policy-changes/>.

⁸ See Jerreat-Poole, “Crip Encounters.”

⁹ In *Predatory Data*, Anita Say Chan explains that from the 1890s on, biometric data would help the United States government conduct eugenics efforts, while at the same time, genetic and health data, “offered concrete means for new kinds of information-empowered classes to metricize deviance” (Chan, *Predatory Data*, 41).

ring. Wearable technology marks one subcategory of “digital health technology” which, drawing from STS and media studies scholars such as Mikki Kressbach and Olivia Banner, I define as any digital technology that records, stores, analyzes, and/or shares information on health, from patient portals to smart watches. Finally, I understand “disability technology” as any device or prosthetic that provides comfort to disabled people and supports or boosts their functionality. While disabled individuals may incorporate wearable technology into their care ecosystem, disability technology and wearable technology are not necessarily synonymous. The relationship between disability and technology is complex, as biometric technologies have long been used to surveil, deny services to, and further debilitate disabled people in institutional, medical, imperial, and military contexts. To begin with, in early- to mid-twentieth century United States, analog biometric data was used by government officials to limit immigration and promote the systemic “sterilization of tens of thousands of individuals who were disproportionately poor, disabled, and minority women.”¹⁰ And in the early stages of computing, major tech companies aided eugenics projects both within the United States and Europe.¹¹

Disability studies and STS scholar Ashley Shew soberly reminds us in *Against Technoableism* that “IBM partnered with Hitler during the Holocaust to help exterminate [and medically experiment on] undesirables,” including disabled people, by reporting “information about ages [at which people had certain] viruses, racial characteristics, disease and disabilities.”¹² In the United States, relationships between the military-industrial complex and medical device manufacturers are, too, long standing. Since the 1940s, for example, ‘treatments’ for mental illness and cognitive disabilities have included “types of electroshock devices used in wartime as torture.”¹³ As Alison Kafer points out in *Feminist, Queer, Crip*, even today it is not uncommon for prosthetics manufacturers to use applications designed for military operations, and vice versa.¹⁴

Despite these confluences between big tech, government, and the medical-industrial complex, disabled people often rely on biotech for safety, assistance, and/or survival.¹⁵ Because it would be impossible for those reliant upon bio- and assistive tech for survival to simply opt out, disabled people often use their prostheses

¹⁰ In *Predatory Data*, Anita Say Chan provides an overview of the early- to mid-twentieth century sterilization laws passed in the United States (2025: 39). Chan also explains that these practices would continue until as late as the 1970s (Chan, *Predatory Data*, 57).

¹¹ See Ashley Shew’s chapter “The Neurodivergent Resistance” from *Against Technoableism* for an analysis of eugenics and early computing.

¹² Ashley Shew, *Against Technoableism: Rethinking Who Needs Improvement. First edition* (New York: W.W. Norton & Company, 2023), 89-90.

¹³ Shew, *Against Technoableism*, 104.

¹⁴ Alison Kafer, *Feminist, Queer, Crip* (Bloomington: Indiana University Press, 2013), 121.

¹⁵ The medical-industrial-complex refers to the assemblage of pharmaceutical, governmental, and institutional entities that determine who receives care and how. See Mia Mingus, “Medical Industrial Complex Visual,” February 6, 2015, <https://leavingevidence.wordpress.com/2015/02/06/medical-industrial-complex-visual/>.

or wearable medical devices creatively to suit evolving, context-specific needs while resisting endemic ableist ideas on how these technologies should be used, and who should be privy to the data they yield. Disabled writer and educator ‘The Cyborg’ Jillian Weise has affectionately termed disabled folks who rely on tech for survival “cyborgs,” reclaiming the term from its cultural misappropriations.¹⁶ Cyborg concerns, Weise contends, include questions such as

“Can I afford my leg? Will a stalker, a doctor or the law kill me?” Cyborg anxieties are perpetuated by the bleak knowledge that, for example, “The insurance company could pull my data and decide I haven’t used my leg enough to justify the next one.”¹⁷

Being cyborg, though, can bring about positive feelings as well. Across the diabetic online community, for example, technology-dependent diabetics will often take to (formerly) Twitter, TikTok, and Instagram to express confidence in being-cyborg thanks to the tech that they use for survival, such as insulin pumps and continuous glucose monitors (CGMs). Often, such display of pride comes in the form of making said tech hyper-visible in images, artwork, and discourse, and encouraging others to do the same.¹⁸ Prideful representations of diabetes tech do not purport that the tech is easy, comfortable, or affordable; rather, these representations subvert normative expectations of bodily comportment. Importantly, displays of pride across the diabetic online community are matched with depictions of the time, energy, and adaptability required by diabetes. That is, living with diabetes—itsself a disease of unpredictability and variability—requires navigating the constraints of extant systems and technologies. Members of the diabetic online community, therefore, also take to social media to offer hacks that extend the lifespan of devices, loop data from CGMs and insulin pumps, and limit the flow of information to healthcare providers and insurance companies. Moreover, diabetics often beat tech manufacturers to programming and software innovations that make their devices more functional. This is evidenced by the “We Are Not Waiting” movement, wherein diabetics across the world develop and share looping and data integration tactics well before these

¹⁶ This reclamation most explicitly appears in The Cyborg Jillian Weise’s 2018 piece for *Granta*, “Common Cyborg.” Weise explains that the “cyborg” is a common figure in literature, film, television, and theory, and that in these contexts, it usually denotes ethical quandaries over or celebration of technological progress, without considering the both the term *cyborg’s* emergence in the 1960s as a referring to biomedical intervention nor offering voice to disabled individuals who necessarily integrated digitized and biometric technologies in their bodies. Weise cites, specifically, Donna Haraway’s “A Cyborg Manifesto” (1985), Anne McCaffery’s *The Ship Who Snag* (1969), and also Google CEO Ray Kurzweil’s futurist proclamations.

¹⁷ Weise, “Common Cyborg,” unpaginated.

¹⁸ On Instagram, for example, the hashtag “#wheresyoursitewednesday” circulates in the diabetic community. Diabetics showcase, typically in image form, where their devices are currently located on their body.

features are officially released via tech manufacturers.¹⁹

Modifying insulin pumps and CGMs is specific to people with diabetes, but similar trends are documented in other Internet spaces, and relating to other assistive devices, such as cochlear implants and prosthetics. Cochlear implant users across TikTok and other social media sites, for example, share tips and tricks for expanding the capacities of their devices, as well as modifying their appearance.²⁰ And some other individuals with implantable medical devices have learned to read and respond to their own data instead of relying on manufacturers' black-boxed algorithms and costly doctors' visits. Such is the case with Hugo Campos, who was diagnosed with hypertrophic cardiomyopathy in 2007. A few years later, after taking a workshop on pacemaker programming, Campos reprogrammed his implantable cardioverter-defibrillator so that he could view his heart rhythm data—usually only available to health providers and device manufactures—and take any necessary precautions on his own. Campos took this step not just because he felt he deserved access to his own health data, but because his health insurance temporarily fell through.²¹ For each user of disability technology, wellbeing is contingent upon an adaptive relationship with technologies, infrastructures, and social systems.

Existing as cyborg can be taxing and costly, but media representations largely imply otherwise. As is well documented by disability scholars, mainstream media often paints disability tech as a quick fix to the problem, and proof of the overall social progress. This is certainly the case with news media, as demonstrated by the abundance of viral clips featuring people with disabilities hearing, speaking, or walking without any issues for the first time, or once again *thanks to* new technologies or applications, with little mention of the cost and discomfort of using such technology, or the forced assimilation that disabled individuals often face.

On TikTok, United States based news program CBS This Morning, for example, shares the story of a woman with non-speaking autism who finds “a legitimate voice” by using a text-to-speech application. ABC World News, also based in the United States, reports: “paralyzed man walks again with the help of AI.”²² While

¹⁹ Dana Lewis and the #OpenAPS Community, “What is #OpenAPS?,” accessed September 2024, <https://openaps.org/>.

²⁰ A search for “cochlear implant hacks” within the TikTok application yields an array of videos on these discussed tips and tricks.

²¹ See Amy Standen, “Patients Crusade for Access to Their Medical Device Data,” *NPR*, May 28, 2012, <https://www.npr.org/sections/health-shots/2012/05/28/153706099/patients-crusade-for-access-to-their-medical-device-data>. See also: “Hugo Campos has Waged a Decade-Long Battle for Access to His Heart Implant,” *The Economist*, September 12, 2019, <https://www.economist.com/technology-quarterly/2019/09/12/hugo-campos-has-waged-a-decade-long-battle-for-access-to-his-heart-implant>.

²² CBS Mornings (@cbsmornings), “At 18, Jordyn Zimmerman’s world opened up when she got hold of a communication app on an iPad for the first time. She is a nonspeaking autistic woman and hadn’t

these technological advents indeed mark significant changes at the individual level that should not be ignored, most mainstream disability tech coverage celebrates normalization and omits issues such as the high cost of such technology and its widespread inaccessibility. As Ashley Shew explains, “So many of our stories about technology and disability are about technologies as redemptive. ...They show us ‘better’ living through technology, where better means something pretty specific about how people exist in the world.” She contends that this concept of “better” is usually based on ableist norms, rather than the desires of disabled people, and that “sometimes the ‘fix’ ends up being too painful or takes too much time; sometimes it is fleeting.”²³ While technology can indeed be lifesaving and life-sustaining for disabled people and people with chronic medical conditions, assimilationist frameworks for development rely on prioritizing what is most desirable for nondisabled people in an ableist society, rather than what is most comfortable or pleasurable for people living with disabilities.

Alongside techno-solutionist narratives, some (primarily nondisabled) content creators on social media have begun to adopt and promote biotech—often referred to as wearable tech or “wearables”—as hopeful means of preventing illness and attaining wellness. In these cases, technology is positioned as a tool which boosts fitness and overall health.²⁴ As disability and gender studies scholar Julie Passanante Elman explains:

Promoting evermore granular health management as a social good, wearables promise greater control over health, safety, and emotional well-being through intimate data gathering. The devices encourage constant but playful self-surveillance; the constant self-enhancement they encourage also offers an endless interface of self-diagnosis.²⁵

The most popular devices championed by wellness creators are smart watches and smart rings, such as Fitbits, Apple Watches, Whoop (bands), and Oura Rings. But sometimes lumped into the language of wearables are devices typically intended for people with autoimmune, endocrine, or cardiac conditions. While interaction with

been able to use her voice to the fullest until then,” video, May 8, 2024, <https://www.tiktok.com/@cbsmornings/video/7366689460366347563>. ABC World News Tonight (@abcworldnews), “A 40-year-old man left #paralyzed after an accident is walking again for the first time in a decade thanks to #brain and #spinalcord implants, and the use of #AI, creating a “digital bridge” to bypass #injured parts of his body.,” video, May 4, 2024, <https://www.tiktok.com/@abcworldnews/video/7237142516854705451>.

²³ See Shew, *Against Technoableism*, 32.

²⁴ This practice is sometimes referred to as “biohacking,” which is most commonly defined as “a do-it-yourself (DIY) form of human enhancement or augmentation, in which people attempt to change aspects of their biology to improve their health, performance, or well-being.” See Caitlin Geng, “What to Know about Biohacking,” *Medical News Today*, October 17, 2022, <https://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/biohacking#overview>.

²⁵ See Julie Passanante Elman, “‘Find Your Fit’: Wearable Technology and the Cultural Politics of Disability,” *New Media & Society* (2018): 3761.

wearables is in many ways “playful,” risks include reifying norms related to embodiment and misrepresenting or trivializing health metrics. Far more than merely being hacks to good health, biometric and wearable technologies encourage constant negotiations of value and norms related to bodily appearance and physical performance.

BIOHACKING AGAINST DISABILITY: A CASE STUDY OF THE CONTINUOUS GLUCOSE MONITOR (CGM)

One popular and contested reappropriation of disability tech in wellness and wearable tech spaces concerns the continuous glucose monitor, or CGM. CGMs are small, semi-subcutaneous devices that capture and present blood glucose (also commonly referred to as “blood sugar”) data in real time, without the logistical hassle of taking finger pricks. They are in many ways liberating, notifying diabetics in advance if they are at risk for a potentially life-threatening blood glucose level (either low or high). However, they also constitute new mechanisms of surveillance and control within the medical-industrial complex. CGM data can, for example, be used by insurance companies, employers, and healthcare providers—each in different ways—to deny care based on assumptions about health, motivation, or lifestyle.²⁶ Thus, the uptake and rebranding of the CGM by nondisabled wellness enthusiasts as a fitness-tracking or weight loss device has not necessarily been warmly received by diabetic communities.

Take, for example, the article published by *The Telegraph* in 2022 entitled “I wore a glucose tracker for two weeks—it's bad news for my favourite breakfast.”²⁷ Its author, Boudicca Fox-Leonard, begins with a confession that serves as a huge red flag to any diabetic reader: “I am not diabetic. Nor am I prediabetic. I do however have a sugar problem.” She identifies that she often feels lethargic during the workday, and wonders, “could my diet be the real problem?”²⁸

Fox-Leonard’s article, moreover, reduces blood sugar data to indices of particular individual choices on diet and exercise when there are, in fact, over thirty factors that affect blood sugar, many of which are environmental or hormonal, and have nothing to do with one’s lifestyle choices.²⁹ In her portrayal of blood sugar fluctuations, Fox-Leonard attributes moral value to choices around food and exercise, falsely putting the blame for the slight blood sugar spikes on her own doing—such as, for example, eating half a banana. She does not once pause to consider how the

²⁶ See Lydia X. Z. Brown, Rihdi Shetty, Matt Scherer, and Andrew Crawford, “Ableism And Disability Discrimination In New Surveillance Technologies: How New Surveillance Technologies in Education, Policing, Health Care, and the Workplace Disproportionately Harm Disabled People” (Washington and Bruxelles: Center for Democracy and Technology, 2022), 40.

fast-paced work culture of which she is part could be affecting her energy or stress levels. The piece, furthermore, instills fear in readers by repeatedly and misleadingly claiming that poor lifestyle choices and obesity alone could cause diabetes. It offers little differentiation between the different types of diabetes and provides zero reference to the genetic and systemic factors that might predispose someone to developing type 2 diabetes.³⁰

Fox-Leonard’s experimentation with diabetes technology was, in sum, offensive because it trivialized blood sugar regulation as a matter of effective meal planning and frequent exercise. Importantly, Fox-Leonard did not mention any of the issues that insulin-dependent diabetics face, such as struggling to access medicine and technology due to extremely high costs or experiencing eating disorders at higher rates due to the social stigma around diabetes. In fact, the American Diabetes Association notes that, on average, women and girls with type 1 diabetes are over twice as likely to develop some form of disordered eating than women and girls without diabetes.³¹ Diabulimia, which is defined as the omission of insulin dosages out of fear that insulin will cause weight gain, has a mortality rate of thirty-four percent.³²

After Fox-Leonard’s article was circulated on Twitter, diabetics took to the platform to air their frustrations. Popular sentiments included messages such as the following:

I really think this would have been better if the writer had spoken to people with diabetes, not called us “diabetes sufferers” or maybe - just not done this at all?³³
 What gets me is the double standard - Non-diabetics can fraudulently obtain CGM’s, the latest most expensive diabetes tech, and yet we are supposed to be happy with insulins developed in the 1980’s or just keep paying \$300 a vial for insulin developed in the 1990s? #Insulin4all³⁴
 There are so many things about this piece which are just ugh! If you don't have Diabetes then you don't need a CGM or Flash. They're not a luxury diet gizmo or “biohack” device.³⁵

²⁷ Boudicca Fox-Leonard, “I wore a glucose tracker for two weeks – it’s bad news my favorite breakfast,” *The Telegraph*, July 26, 2022, <https://www.telegraph.co.uk/health-fitness/conditions/diabetes/wore-glucose-tracker-two-weeks-bad-news-favourite-breakfast/>.

²⁸ Fox-Leonard, “I wore a glucose tracker,” unpaginated.

²⁹ See Adam Brown, “42 Factors That Affect Blood Glucose?! A Surprising Update,” *diaTribe*, September 29, 2022, <https://diatribe.org/diabetes-management/42-factors-affect-blood-glucose-surprising-update/>.

³⁰ See Tashi Dendup et al., “Environmental Risk Factors for Developing Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus: A Systematic Review,” *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 15, no. 1 (2018): 78, <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/15/1/78>.

³¹ See “Types of Eating Disorders,” *American Diabetes Association*, September 2024, <https://diabetes.org/health-wellness/mental-health/eating-disorders>.

³² See “What is Diabulimia? | Signs, Symptoms, Risk Factors & Treatment,” *National Alliance for Eating Disorders*, October 31, 2024, <https://www.allianceforeatingdisorders.com/what-is-diabulimia/>.

³³ Lauren Turner (@thisislaurent), Twitter (now X), July 26, 2022, <https://x.com/thisislaurent/status/1551861309364396037>.

³⁴ Miss Diabetes (@miss__diabetes), Twitter (now X), July 26, 2022, https://x.com/miss__diabetes/status/1552044274794958849.

Of course, Fox-Leonard's off-key exploration of CGMs represents just one trend within a larger world of "wellness" discourse. I belabor this example here to showcase how, while experimentation with emerging biotech might seem like a harmless mechanism of self-evaluation and disease prevention, encoded in the language of this experimentation is often an ableist, misleading, and exclusive discourse about the right way to live.

To be sure though, it is not, at the outset, problematic to simply want to feel better and healthier. If technology *might* be able to do that, why not incorporate it? And further, why *can't* we see biohacking as a form of resistance to capitalism's processes of wearing down? Indeed, under mature capitalism, we live in conditions of increasing precarity. Cultural theorist Lauren Berlant explains, "capitalist activity always induces destabilizing scenes of productive destruction—of resources and of lives being made and unmade according to the dictates and whims of the market." They add, "neoliberal economic practices mobilize this instability in unprecedented ways," including cuts to social welfare programs, limits on workplace unionization, and resource privatization.³⁶ Labor precarities wrought by neoliberal policies of the past several decades have contributed to legitimate anxieties and shifting attitudes around safety, stability, and health, which are sometimes channeled through technophilic attachments and fantasies.

Even among the most financially privileged members of society, fear mongering around health, illness, and diagnosis abounds in online spaces. As disability studies scholar Amy Gaeta has noted, whether we identify as disabled or not, we are constantly interpellated—that is, hailed or identified—as needing intervention through health capitalism. Social media surveillance, Gaeta contends, creates phantom disabilities through diagnostic advertisements, wherein algorithms serve up auto-generated targeted ads for devices, therapies, and services related to mental and physical health conditions users have not been diagnosed with, but rather associated with based on their search and viewing trends.³⁷ It is not hard to see how, amidst a flurry of bodily and psychological self-re-evaluations, biotech that indicates whether daily activities and bodily processes are, allegedly, normal, healthy, and in range may seem desirable.

The problem with casualized biomonitoring through wearable tech and corresponding health applications lies not in the curiosity over bodily data at the level of the individual user. Rather, what becomes problematic in the culture of wearables is its focus on individual metrics and behaviors as the answer to health crises and related anxieties in a capitalist society. Hobby biomonitoring, I am arguing, can

³⁵ Diabetic Dad (@DiabeticDadUK), "Twitter (now X), July 26, 2021, <https://x.com/DiabeticDadUK/status/1551870058300948480>.

³⁶ See Lauren Berlant, *Cruel Optimism* (Durham: Duke University Press, 2011), 192.

³⁷ See Amy Gaeta, "Diagnostic Advertisements: The Phantom Disabilities Created by Social Media Surveillance," *First Monday* 28, no. 1 (2023): unpaginated. DOI:10.5210/fm.v28i1.12913.

be seen as indicative of the longstanding class divisions related to technologies of self-affirmation. Wearables culture is in fact an extension of wellness culture that took hold in post-WWII United States and Europe. Historian Daniela Blei explains that the idea of wellness gained popularity in the late 1950s, with the rise in “capitalist expansion, wealth concentration, labor insecurity, and with it, status anxiety,” and has since only expanded in reach and influence.³⁸ Over the past decade, with the emergence of the platform economy and digital health technologies, wellness—and its regimes of self-monitoring, moderation, individualism, and restraint—has found footing in the wearables market. In its emphasis on individualized tracking—or self-surveillance as a necessary means of obtaining and maintaining health—wearables culture excludes those without the time, money, or bodily capacity to comply. Furthermore, wearables culture obscures systemic issues that may be contributing to fatigue and gradual damage to the body.

For example, when *Telegraph* author Boudicca Fox-Leonard cites her diet and marginally elevated blood glucose as the likely reason for her afternoon brain fog, she not only assigns moral value to certain biometrics, but also forecloses conversations around the structure of the capitalist workday and its impact on one’s capacity to rest.³⁹ So too do other wearables enthusiasts and wellness creators who promote the idea that individual step counts, sleep stats, and dietary choices are the key to betterment.

WEARABLE TECH ON TIKTOK: METHODS AND OVERVIEW

Methods

To gain a broader understanding of how wearable tech enthusiasts and tech companies manufacture ableist norms around health and wellness, I utilized traditional close reading methods, computational processes, and digital humanities tools to analyze discussions around “wearable tech,” “disability,” and “disability precarity” on TikTok.⁴⁰ My TikTok exploration began back in Spring 2023. I started collecting data manually, by feeding my keywords—wearable tech, disability, and disability precarity—into the “search” feature while logged into my personal account, and then recording my observations in a spreadsheet. From there, with the help of Deen Freelon’s “Pyktok” module in python, I began scraping metadata related to the “top”

³⁸ Daniela Blei, “The False Promise of Wellness culture,” *JSTOR Daily*, para. 13, <https://daily.jstor.org/the-false-promises-of-wellness-culture/>.

³⁹ Specifically, Fox-Leonard says, “I wonder if the general brain fog I feel towards the end of the day is less tiredness than being dosed up on sugar?” Fox-Leonard, “I wore a glucose tracker for two weeks,” 2022.

⁴⁰ My decision to seek out TikTok data and employ a combination of close-reading and web scraping methods was influenced by Lindsay Thomas’s “BookTok and the Rituals of Recommendation,” *Post45*, December 18, 2023, <https://post45.org/2023/12/booktok-and-the-rituals-of-recommendation/>.

videos yielded by my keyword.⁴¹ To scale up my sample, I downloaded metadata and comments from TikTok videos related to my search terms using data extractors within the platform Apify.⁴² In order to identify and better understand wearables trends, I recorded and transcribed audio for over two-hundred unique TikTok videos using Zoom (by playing videos while I was “hosting” a personal Zoom meeting). Finally, I utilized the digital humanities platform Voyant to perform a text analysis on transcribed audio.⁴³

My sample is limited to English-language TikTok videos and comments. While links to TikTok videos and other media content have been provided in footnotes, I refrain from referring to creators by name in-text due to the personal, health-focused nature of expressed sentiments. Consistent with scholarship in digital studies, media studies, and literary and cultural studies, I use the term “creators” to refer to individual TikTok users who produce videos.

Findings

To little surprise, I found that much of the discussion around wearable tech and bio-monitoring among nondisabled social media users is focused on the *optimization* of certain daily and typical bodily activities. Topics of interest to wearable tech enthusiasts include sleep and recovery data; menstrual cycle tracking; diet tracking and insights; and stress indices. When I used Voyant to mine transcribed audio from one hundred “top” TikTok videos yielded by my “wearable tech” keyword search, I found that most frequently used terms included *sleep, smart, heath, ai, and data*.⁴⁴ While four of the one hundred creators discuss technology specifically in the context of illness or disability, most creators instead cite desires to reach wellness goals. TikTok creators profess, for example:

“I’ve been wearing my Whoop to monitor my health, recovery, and sleep... I’m able to optimize my health and fitness as well as get personalized Performance Coaching based on my data”⁴⁵

⁴¹ See Deen Freelon, “Pyktok: A simple module to collect video, text, and metadata from TikTok,” GitHub, nd, <https://github.com/dfreelon/pyktok>.

⁴² See <https://apify.com/clockworks/free-tiktok-scraper> and <https://apify.com/clockworks/tiktok-comments-scraper>.

⁴³ See <https://voyant-tools.org/>.

⁴⁴ The videos commented on in this overview were generated by a search for “wearable tech” within my personal research account on my personal computer in the southeastern United States. I used Zoom to download audio transcriptions and www.voyant-tools.org to identify frequent terms and sentiments.

⁴⁵ summer araya (@summer.marshall), “my favorite wearable technology on & off the golf course |Woman Golfing Emojil Shop the @WHOOP cyber sale going on now! #whoop #ad #WHOOPpartner,” video, November 27, 2023, <https://www.tiktok.com/@summer.marshall/video/7306229286095097131>.

“I have become a sleeping professional.”⁴⁶

“...I like how they give you tips on how to improve your sleep. I also like how it gives you very prescriptive feedback.”⁴⁷

“...if you can experiment in the right doses, you can actually change how you feel.”⁴⁸

One common topic among wearable tech enthusiasts was a new device called the “Ultrahuman Ring.” The Ultrahuman Ring is a competitor to the “Oura Ring” and “Samsung Galaxy Ring,” and is part of an emerging class of wearables that, as the name suggests, take the form of a ring rather than a watch, band, or sensor. Ultrahuman Ring reviewers enjoy features such as “sleep score,” “readiness score,” “sleep debt,” “stress rhythm score,” “stress levels,” “cardio age,” and cycle tracking.⁴⁹ These scores and estimates are based on metrics such as heart rate, blood pressure, blood oxygen levels, skin temperature, and environmental stimuli, which allow the ring to detect whether wearers are, say, asleep, at rest, or physiologically stressed. Wearers explain that the ring not only tracks biometric data but performs analyses and responds (via phone application) in kind, offering prompts such as “time to unwind” or “avoid heavy meals right now.” In addition to its built-in features, according to the company website, the device has the capacity to connect with other health monitors—and offer feedback based on those external readings.

As for its medical applications, reviewers of the Ultrahuman Ring on TikTok seldom explicitly identify as disabled or cite *disability*. Some wearers do, however, discuss specific health and reproductive conditions. One content creator, for instance, names PCOS as a cause for increased interest in healthy habits, and another hopes the ring will help indicate pregnancy after IVF therapy. Similarly, many TikTok reviewers of the Ultrahuman Ring’s competitor, the Oura Ring, express that while they do not care for the amount of information yielded by the Oura App related to sleep, stress, and miscellaneous biometrics, they continue to wear the Oura Ring because it serves as their *only* form of birth control. While not typically framed in the context of mental illness, stress management—and the tracking of stress cycles and stress scores—is a commonly listed perk across creators.

⁴⁶ Sweats & the City (@sweatsandthecity), “Honest review of @ouraring #ouraring #techreview #oura #wearabletech #review #foryoupage #sleepoptimization #health #healthyliving #longevity #greenscreen,” video, August 18, 2022, <https://www.tik-tok.com/@sweatsandthecity/video/7133294399286529323>.

⁴⁷ eggdressesup (@eggdressesup), “now that the new year new me phase is coming up I wanted to talk about this ring I’ve been wearing for a few months [Slightly Smiling Face Emoji] not sponsored btw! honest review #ultrahumanringair,” video, December 27, 2024, <https://www.tiktok.com/@eggdressesup/video/7453164632333651243>.

⁴⁸ Danny Miranda (@heydannymiranda), “Have you tried either of these? #ouraring #whoopband #wearabletech #sleeptech #sleeptechlife #magnesium #sleephygiene #dannymirandapodcast,” video, August 15, 2022, <https://www.tiktok.com/@heydannymi-randa/video/7132133218366524715>.

⁴⁹ To learn about the Ultrahuman Ring, I explored TikTok reviews of the product using my own personal TikTok account, logged into my iPhone in the southeastern United States.

Often, creators note a sense of comfort or reassurance in having data to explain how they are feeling, or how they might feel better. Wearables, through their transformation of bodily activity into numerical indices of health and wellness, affirm or alter users' daily choices about what to eat, for example, or when to exercise or rest. Feedback from wearables is indeed, as one creator notes, "prescriptive," and adds up to an overall encouragement to organize time, energy, and consumption so that each available indicator of wellness is achieved.

While most of the health tracking device reviews that I encountered on TikTok were enthusiastic about wearables, some were marked by a more ambivalent stance. When, for example, one popular creator revealed that she was parting from her Oura Ring, her viewers offered mixed opinions on the utility of smart rings. One commenter noted, "I'm the opposite. I NEED it. It tracks everything for me and knows I'm sick before I do. [Woman Shrugging Emoji, Female Sign Emoji]"⁵⁰ But the video creator explained that for her, the data and reflections proffered by the ring made it hard to tell how she was *really* feeling; if the ring told her she was not well-rested by giving her a low sleep or readiness score, for example, she would begin her day anxious and discouraged. In turn, the term "anxiety" appeared over fifty times in the corpus of roughly 1,600 comments responding to the popular TikToker's-video and follow-up response. Many commenters explicitly endorse the creator's anxiety-related shedding of her wearable, explaining that their devices also heightened feelings of alarm, created new health anxieties, or triggered former disordered eating and exercise habits.

ANALYSIS: BIASES AND RISKS OF WEARABLE TECH

While disability is not a central feature of discussion in relation to wearables on TikTok, the desires to understand sites of dysfunction, deficiency, imbalance, or excess within the body are often noted. Users rely on their technology to prescribe ways to correct perceived deficiencies and imperfections. Importantly, the standards and recommendations set by wearables, though at least in part informed by biomedical sciences, typically "assume that bodies fit within a certain range of variation, that bodily functions follow a regular pattern that allows algorithms to turn into physiology data," and "that gendered and racialized bodies can be detached from their social, cultural, and geopolitical locations."⁵¹ And where specialization is availa

⁵⁰ Olivia Boblet (@oliviaboblet), "Curious to see how i feel bc I CANT," video, January 15, 2025, <https://www.tiktok.com/@oliviaboblet/video/7460327309602491690>. Olivia Boblet (@oliviaboblet), "Replying to @Emily so this is how im feeling and its OK if you dont agree," video, January 16, 2025, <https://www.tiktok.com/@oliviaboblet/video/7460547873726532910>.

⁵¹ See Luna Dolezal and Venla Oikkinen, "Introduction: Self-Tracking, Embodied Differences, and Intersectionality," *Catalyst: Feminism, Theory, and Technoscience* 7, no. 1 (2021): 4.

ble—such as in reproductive health or mental health monitoring—normative assumptions still shape available metrics, goals, and recommendations.⁵²

Most users, based on my analysis of trending TikTok reviews, do not incorporate wearable tech because of a particular health issue they hope to resolve, but rather as a preventative and exploratory measure recommended to them by algorithmic social media encounters. However, in *Sensing Health: Bodies, Data and Digital Technologies*, Mikki Kressbach notes that, even where wearables are taken up out of concern for what have been dubbed “lifestyle diseases,” their embedded programs often conflate the goals of disease prevention and individual improvement, encouraging users to tie their perception of wellbeing not just to preventative action but also to competitive hyperachievement.⁵³ In this way, Kressbach argues, “individuals who ascribe to these systems end up caught up in a never-ending cycle of accumulation and improvement; and by extension, health becomes framed through the logic of capital,” where status is achieved through exertion, accumulation, and quantitative valuation.⁵⁴ As participation within this process is dependent upon time, resources, and bodily capacity, the risk and reward of wearables integration is unevenly distributed across class and ability.

Similar to Gaeta's earlier-mentioned findings, Olivia Banner explains in “Disability Studies, Big Data and Algorithmic Culture” that disability is one of many “algorithmic identities” tracked by big tech. If a user of a wearable or health app, for example, clocks certain metrics or “likes” content pertaining to mental health or chronic illness, they might be served up more advertisements for health technologies or notified more intrusively by their devices of perceived irregularities that need attention.⁵⁵ More problematically, as wearables are increasingly tied into employer and government wellness programs in the United States and Europe, failure or inability to opt into tracking programs or meet company-wide fitness incentives could mean that disabled employees pay more for healthcare than their peers.⁵⁶ Furthermore, while wellness programs generally cannot request “disability-specific” information, the incentivization to reach certain metrics related to blood pressure, step count, weight, or cholesterol may target or all but exclude disabled workers and users, thus subjecting them to potential scrutiny and implicit discrimination. Finally, the Center for Democracy and Technology explains that, at least in the United States, biometric tracking coded as “wellness,” operates in a murky legal zone. That is, because information from wearables is not necessarily protected by the Health

⁵² Dolezal and Oikkenen, “Introduction,” 4.

⁵³ Mikki Kressbach, *Sensing Health: Bodies, Data, and Digital Health Technologies* (Michigan: University of Michigan Press, 2024), 14-17.

⁵⁴ Kressbach, *Sensing Health*, 17.

⁵⁵ Olivia Banner, “Disability Studies, Big Data, and Algorithmic Culture,” in *Interdisciplinary Approaches to Disability: Looking Towards the Future*, ed. Ellis, Katie, Rosemarie Garland-Thomson, Mike Kent, and Rachel Robertson (New York: Routledge, 2019), 49.

⁵⁶ Elman, “Find Your Fit,” 3769.

Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA), it is subject to third party sharing.⁵⁷ This could have implications not only for disabled people but also for other minoritized people trying to access care such as contraceptives, or hormone therapy.

In addition, there is a financial component to the standards and metrics of wearables: those who are overworked, who have been denied medical care, or who *cannot* access rest because they are attending to precarious financial situations at the same time as they are performing care work might *also* be perceived through a pathologizing framework. The demands of wearables seem impossible: sleep *more*, move *more*, stress *less*, eat *better*, and participate sufficiently within capitalism through acceptable forms of labor (so that, for one, you can afford the healthy lifestyle demanded of you). Ironically, though, the more personal, *nonlabor* time one has—which often translates into financial privilege—the more they can focus on bettering their health. That is, the more free time users have to comply with and track progress toward the demands of wellness culture, the more data (casualized labor) they have to give to health tech companies, and in turn, the better they can reinforce these norms through their platforms and social networks.

In *Communicative Biocapitalism*, Olivia Banner asserts that “the dysfunction of our healthcare system benefits communicative capitalism.”⁵⁸ Banner acknowledges that traditional and in-person forms of healthcare are becoming less accessible and more expensive and timely. Because of this, she explains, we increasingly turn to communications technologies designed to collect and share health data, from patient portals and FAQ sites, to wearables and their compatible apps. She refers to the growing networks of digital health markets as *communicative biocapitalism*, a system designed to profit from the body-as-data. Digital health technologies such as wearables ultimately help to fuel capitalist ends, encouraging employees to work more efficiently in traditional employment settings, but also to generate more data and profit for health tech platforms. This means that, not only do digital health technologies such as wearables shore up new ways to affirm nondisabled, ‘productive’ users/consumer/workers, but they also introduce new ways of collecting and profiting from data obtained from both nondisabled and disabled users, by framing them as in need of continual improvement.⁵⁹

⁵⁷ See Brown et al., “Ableism and Disability Discrimination,” 55.

⁵⁸ Olivia Banner, *Communicative Biocapitalism: The Voice of the Patient in Digital Health and the Health Humanities* (Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press), 12.

⁵⁹ See Elman, “Find Your Fit,” 3774.

CONCLUSION: REFRAMING DISABILITY PRECARITY

Digital health technologies, operating as part of a larger capitalist system, do not only affirm perceived nondisabled bodies, but also create new sites of vulnerability and precarity for disabled people. Paradoxically, where wellness programs through employers and insurers promote and reimburse fitness wearables, such programs of reward and reimbursement do not work the same way in the context of disability technology, or when disabled people employ wearables as part of their care ecosystem. Instead, obtaining prescriptions and authorizations for disability technologies—such as CGMs, continuous positive airway machines (CPAPs), oxygen machines—usually requires intense and invasive documentation to begin with (such as months’ worth of health data, which can be both time consuming and emotionally burdensome to collect); and access to disability tech is always contingent upon a certain level of perceived patient compliance and need, as evaluated and established by healthcare providers and insurance companies. Relationships between patients and medical technologies, moreover, are increasingly surveilled, and can be used by insurers to determine coverage or increase premiums.⁶⁰ Privacy related to health information is, then, not a matter of choice—simply opting in or out—as it is for non-disabled tech users.

Beyond issues of privacy and surveillance, disabled people frequently have trouble accessing vital technologies because they are expensive and private insurance is often connected to full-time labor—something that might be inaccessible to disabled people in the first place. In the United States, Medicare and Medicaid often do not cover the kinds of assistive technologies that popular media suggest will fix or eradicate disability. Even for disabled people with financial privilege and access to a full range of treatment options, biometric devices can be physically uncomfortable and emotionally distressing, especially when they yield immediate, important health data.

In her discussion of disability precarity back in 2023, Alice Wong shared her anxieties, confessing: “I feel like a lot of disabled people like me are constantly treading water... when one thing happens a cascade of others creates utter chaos #DisabilityPrecarity.”⁶¹ Others agreed, offering experiences such as:

... I live my life month to month - where is my insulin refill coming from, is my insulin pump in warranty, do we have enough functioning infrastructure to get me a replacement or meds via mail, what happens if I lose my job and can't access insurance...⁶²

⁶⁰ Brown et al., “Ableism and Disability Discrimination,” 44.

⁶¹ Alice Wong 王美華 (@SFdirewolf), “Last night two of medical devices/equipment I rely on to live malfunctioned...” Twitter (now X), September 10, 2023, <https://x.com/SFdirewolf/status/1700958782308962527>.

And while wellness influencers often cite better sleep as an effect of smart tech, one Twitter user explains in response to Wong, “I use a CPAP at night and there is a HUGE difference in sleep quality when I don’t use it [Melting Face Emoji].”⁶³ This expression of legitimate need serves as a counterpoint to manufactured reliance upon sleep data, such as sleep and readiness scores, vis-à-vis wearable tech such as the Oura and Ultrahuman rings.

Relatedly, on TikTok, disabled creators who share content connected to disability or disability precarity often express concerns over work, benefits, insurance denials, and access.⁶⁴ One creator notes that their insurance provider has deemed their vital respiration technology too expensive and thus they may be moved to a care home. Others cite limitations on the amount of working hours, or documented savings they are allowed to have to still receive coverage for day-to-day health expenses and technology. “Work”, in fact, appears over one hundred times across one hundred TikTok videos related to disability or disability precarity. Definitely, some creators cite how inaccessible infrastructure such as lack of sidewalks and ramps, or possibly ableist policies such as no-cellphone policies in schools, make it challenging to use adaptive technology in public spaces.

Technological integration is more likely to be necessary in tangible and immediate ways for disabled people, and at the same time, it is also more likely to facilitate privacy intrusions, create financial strain, and draw stigma. We see that technological integration through wearables such as smart watches, bands, and rings is heralded as part of a greater wellness effort by nondisabled creators, consumers, and workers. Meanwhile, disabled people who attempt to access health technologies for the purposes of survival, safety, and comfort are questioned by employers, government agencies, and insurance companies. The two phenomena—I draw on disability studies, media studies, and science and technologies studies to argue—are connected due to the increasing propensity for policy makers and economic superpowers to link health to individual choices and personal responsibility. In turn, policy makers enable the expansion of digital health technologies within the capitalist market, and at the same time, cut funding for disability resources, benefits, and research. Digital health technologies and the media ecosystems of which they are a part further reinforce ableist biases by influencing users to grow attachments to systems of feedback and reward based on individual actions. This focus serves as a distraction from systemic issues that contribute to feelings of fatigue and exposure to illness, and at the same time promulgate feelings of inadequacy.

⁶² Kat S (@KatSDC), Twitter (now X), Sept 10, 2023, <https://x.com/KatSDC/status/1701052069962990021>.

⁶³ annaham.bsky.social (@annaham360), “...Only a part-time cyborg, but still!,” Twitter (now X), September 10, 2023, <https://x.com/annaham360/status/1700968766883180961>.

⁶⁴ To identify said TikTok videos, I used my personal research TikTok account, on my personal computer while located in the southeastern United States, to search “disability precarity.” I then used audio from videos obtained by my search to mine sentiments using Voyant.

In light of these developments, it is worth continuing to press on contradictions between wellness cultures' claims about the utility of wearable technologies for health insights and disabled users' experiences navigating both everyday and disability-specific technology. It is also important to keep asking how we might shift public discussion on wellbeing toward systemic changes and better tech for every-one, rather than only those already read as fit for participation in normative and pro-ductive realms of capitalism. ▣

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